

The “Long 2020”: The Unfolding Geopolitical Transition of the World Order

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Abstract:

World orders might be relatively static, but they do change – and when a change occurs it triggers significant shocks throughout the world geopolitical system. We are acquainted with many different explanations to how such changes occur, be it Modelski’s Long Cycles, Organski’s power transition or Kennedy’s imperial overstretch. But while they all provide explanations to why and how the process of geopolitical system change happens, what they all lack is an understanding of how geopolitical structure impacts state behavior during these relatively short periods between two world orders. This is where Peter Taylor’s notion of geopolitical transition comes in. According to Taylor geopolitical transition represents a short time span in which radical restructuring of the international system occurs. Just as Taylor highlighted the “Long 1945” as the moment of geopolitical transition from the *Interbellum* geopolitical system to the (then) emerging Cold War geopolitical system, we hypothesize that we are now in the period of geopolitical transition - The “Long 2020”, moment between the *Pax Americanna* geopolitical system and the emerging geopolitical system whose characteristics are yet to be defined. Thus, the objective of this paper is three-fold. Firstly, we will provide an overview of the concept of geopolitical transition. Secondly, we will provide arguments to why we are currently living in such a period dubbed as the Long 2020. Finally, we will touch upon the implications of how structural uncertainty during periods of geopolitical transition impact the behavior of states.

Key Words:

Geopolitical transition, World Order, geopolitical system, U.S., China, Russia, COVID-19, Russo-Ukrainian war

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A Brief Introduction

Few phrases gather so much attention both in academia and public discourse as world order. It is somewhat understandable why. The grandiosity behind this phrase stems from the fact that world order represents an overarching idea that gives context in which state interactions unfold. While this is by no means a definition of the concept of world order, it shows why so much attention is given to it. Akin to the rules of any game, world order is thought of as impacting everyone, everywhere, doing everything – and does so for a prolonged period of time. However, what happens during periods when one order changes to another? The central claim of this paper is that we are currently living in such a period – a period when the Liberal Order is transitioning to a new world order.

In geopolitics, such a process of transition between two orders is called geopolitical transition. It is a relatively short but rapid period of change in the way the world geopolitical system is structured (Taylor, 1990). During a span of a few years, geopolitical system goes through a rapid change marked with an increase in intrastate conflicts, change in alignment patterns and the shape of international institutions and regimes. This paper argues that ever since the COVID-19 pandemic began, the world entered a period of geopolitical transition – and we are still there. Following Peter Taylor’s label “The Long 1945”, used to signify the geopolitical transition to the Cold War Liberal Order, we call this period “The Long 2020” – highlighting how COVID-19 pandemic represented a similar turning point as the end of the Second World War did.

More concretely, in this paper we put forth three propositions regarding the current state of the world order. Firstly, the geopolitical view of world order allows for a better understanding of the interplay between world order and state behavior. By downplaying the “merits” of parsimonious generalities and thinking about world order through spatial lens we avoid thinking in a void (see: Booth, 1979, p. 147). Secondly, the rapid rise and unexpectedness of international conflicts following 2020 provides a clear sign that we are living in a moment of geopolitical transition. World order manages international competition. When the number and intensity of conflicts increase, and they do so unexpectedly for most observers, the managing effect of world order ceases and new order emerges. Finally, being in a period of geopolitical transition implies that international conflicts will

Geopolitics and the world system

The distinction of different types of international systems in more mainstream IR theory is relatively simple. Since Kenneth Waltz onwards, the international system has been observed namely through the given distribution of power and the number

of poles of such an international system (Waltz, 2010). Even if we take the English School's approach to international society, which is somewhat more detailed in its explanation of the structural effects, it is still overly parsimonious to encapsulate the full complexity of the international system (e.g. see Jervis, 1999). Simply put, IR theories focus either on power distribution, or international organizations and regimes, or the societal agreement on how states should behave. However, in the quest for theoretical parsimony and abstract generality they tend to miss out on how they intertwine and actually impact the world.

Geopolitics does this differently. Firstly, the defining characteristic of Geopolitics, compared to other approaches to the study of international politics, is that it sees spatial factors as the main driving force of state behavior. Yet, space need not relate to locations, natural resources, physical barriers, etc. as it is usually perceived. How individuals and groups perceive different spatial areas, how space is represented in popular culture, and even how global space itself is politically organized, can likewise be thought of as the spatial factors of geopolitics. Geopolitics is therefore best defined as the spatial analysis of international politics, whereas spatial factors are broadly defined.

Within the broader geopolitical approach, structural geopolitics studies how the spatial structure of the world geopolitical system conditions state behavior. We must note that the meaning of structural geopolitics (within geopolitical studies) is somewhat uncertain. While some authors like O'Tuathail mention it in their heuristic division of geopolitics (alongside formal, practical, and popular), most exclude structural geopolitics from the division. It is our understanding that structural geopolitics encompasses precisely the study of structural characteristics of the given geopolitical system and bases its explanation on state behavior through the influence on them by the geopolitical system itself. Therefore, any author who gives explanatory advantage to the structural/systemic factors or any conceptual/theoretical apparatus that highlights the global scale can be considered part of study of structural geopolitics (e.g. see: Cohen, 1975; 2015; Agnew and Corbridge, 1995; Dussouy, 2010; Taylor, 1990; 1993) The world geopolitical system represents the way in which space is organized on the highest scale – global. It is produced by the practices of and interactions between states as well as the collective imaginations on “how the world works”. This represents the “environmental, spatial frame” in which all state behavior occurs, and concrete characteristics of a given geopolitical system dictates the span of possibilities and limitations on state behavior.

Benefits of utilizing structural geopolitics

The previous discussion should be understood as the foundation to why the geopolitical approach to international politics is used, instead of IR theories.

Geopolitics avoids what John Agnew calls “the territorial trap” of IR, the notion that the international environment as a “set of fixed facts setting the environment for the action of territorial states that are essentially the same today as 200 years ago” (Agnew, 1994, p. 56). For the purposes of this paper, there are three main arguments as to why utilizing structural geopolitical approaches can provide us with a better understanding of the changing world order.

Firstly, although international systems can be categorized by polarity, the environment in which states operate is not always the same. Even minute changes of the environment, albeit of the same polarity-type, can impact the behavior of states. To say that the international system is unipolar, bipolar or multipolar not only gives us a wide range of possible state behavior, but we can also state that the same state behavior can, hypothetically, have quite different patterns of implementation as well as geographical focus. Take for an example Southeast Asia. The bipolar nature of the Cold War international system does not tell us much as to why it became such a foreground of proxy wars between the U.S. and U.S.S.R. and not, for an example, the Middle East or Northeast Asia or Central Asia. All these regions could have been (and in certain points of the Cold War were) the place of most prominent activity in implementing Containment. Yet, when we now say Domino Theory the first region that comes to mind is Southeast Asia. Some can argue that this is just how it is – in the sense that proxy wars were inevitable in the Cold War bipolar structure and in Southeast Asia. However, this cannot be seen as given. A myriad of factors, both external and internal to the region, had led to Southeast Asia being the focal point.

Secondly, the geopolitical system shifts are not something that happens overnight. Just observe the current state of the international system. There is no consensus whether we live in a unipolar, bipolar or a multipolar world. The lack of consensus stems from the fact that there is a vast gray zone in between different possible states of polarity in the international system. What happens before we enter the gray zone and what happens after we exit it, is easier to comprehend. But effects on state behavior during structural shifts are something that precisely happens in that black box of a gray zone. This directly connects to the second point. Even though states can be revisionist or status quo, the differences in the international environment impact not only what states prefer/don't prefer in the current international system but also precisely (as possible) what they wish to keep/change. Finally, relying on geopolitics gives us a conceptual apparatus for observing the black box of geopolitical system shifts gray zone – the concept of geopolitical transition.

Finally, another important note that differentiates the geopolitical view of the international system from the IR one is that the materialist-idealist divide need not exist. Sure, some IR theories would argue this as well, but this is something virtually built into the geopolitical view of international politics. Simply put, both space and

geography, that study spatial differentiations, rest upon physical as well as human characteristics. Those who would raise an objection by stating that geopolitics highlights only the physical side of space in providing explanations of international politics have quite a reductionist view of geopolitics that knows only the likes of Mackinder and Spykman – works a century old.

Conceptualizing geopolitical world system

Among different theoretical approaches in structural geopolitics, Saul Bernard Cohen's approach stands tall as a particularly well envisioned way to observe the world geopolitical system. Cohen sees the world as a set of hierarchically nested spatial wholes – ranging from the subnational regions, to states, geopolitical regions and geostrategic realms (Cohen, 2015, p. 37). Each spatial whole is defined by geopolitical features and patterns – features being “political-geographical nodes, areas and boundaries that contribute to the unit's uniqueness and influence its cohesiveness” (Cohen, 2015, p. 37) while patterns refer to “the shape, size and the physical/human geographical characteristics of the geopolitical units and the networks that tie them together...and...distinguish them from other units” (Cohen, 2015, p. 37). Geostrategic realms are at the highest spatial level that includes multiple geopolitical regions. They are geostrategic because only strategic interactions exist between them. According to Cohen, there are currently three geostrategic realms: Maritime realm – led by the U.S.; Eurasian continental realm – led by Russia; and East Asian realm – led by China (Cohen, 2015). Outside this framework, there exist independent geopolitical regions (only South Asia led by India), shatterbelts (internally fragmented and strategically located geopolitical regions that are caught in a competition between great powers), compression zones (similar to shatterbelts but caught in a competition between regional powers), gateway regions (that can serve as a place of cooperation between competing great powers) and convergence zones (regions which can lean either way) (Cohen, 2015, p. 37-63; Kopanja, 2020).

Observing the world geopolitical system in a certain period of time, a distinct geopolitical structure emerges – structure that is unique in its shape and characteristics. Although two separate world geopolitical systems can be thought of as unipolar/bipolar/multipolar, they are still distinct in their shape and characteristics. It is therefore that the impact of structural factors on the direction of a certain state's grand strategy becomes more evident. Likewise the strategic vision of a state becomes easier to determine, because it directly relates to the (relatively) concrete structure of the geopolitical system one state strives to achieve. Similarly, it gives us a better understanding of what makes a given state revisionist or status quo.

Although Cohen's approach to the world geopolitical system provides us with a better foothold for observing the impact of structural factors on grand strategy, it is (of course) not perfect and has issues of its own (see: Kopanja, 2020). One of the most important problems is that the model itself completely ignores the collective imaginations on how the world works. This point can be supplemented by another structural geopolitical approach by John Agnew and Stuart Corbridge. Unlike Cohen's detailed view of the geopolitical system, Agnew and Corbridge provide a relatively reductionist view of it through the notion of geopolitical order (Agnew and Corbridge, 1995). But what they lack in precision with the notion of geopolitical order, they more than compensate with the idea of a global geopolitical discourse.

For Agnew and Corbridge, global geopolitical discourse represents "how the geography of the international political economy has been 'written and read' in the practices of foreign and economic policies during different periods of geopolitical order" (Agnew and Corbridge, 1995, p. 46). In essence, this would mean that each geopolitical system has an overreaching discourse attached to it that induces specific geographical representations both into the practices of states as well as the communication between states (Agnew and Corbridge, 1995, pp. 46-47). The global geopolitical discourse impacts how states and their political leaders envision the current spatial distribution of power, legitimate courses of action, delineate between friend and foe and generally observe how states should interact. Insofar, Agnew and Corbridge identified three global geopolitical discourses: Civilizational (1815-1875), Naturalized (1875-1945) and Ideological (1945-1990), each succeeding one another following geopolitical system shifts (Agnew and Corbridge, 1995, pp. 52-76). With the introduction of global geopolitical discourse along with Cohen's view of the structure of the world geopolitical system we get a more complete geopolitical view of the international system.

The "Long 2020": Geopolitical Transition in Action

The main hypothesis of this paper is that that we are currently living in the period of geopolitical transition – the "Long 2020". Just as Taylor highlighted the "Long 1945" as the moment of geopolitical transition from the *Interbellum* geopolitical system to the (then) emerging Cold War geopolitical system, we are now in the period of geopolitical transition between the *Pax Americana* geopolitical system and the emerging geopolitical system whose characteristics are yet to be defined. The name – "Long 2020", immediately brings to mind the idea that the COVID-19 pandemic was the main driving force behind geopolitical transition. This is not the case. COVID-19 was just a trigger that expedited the process and brought the period of geopolitical transition quicker than it would have happened if there were no pandemic. Think of it in terms of the causes of the First World War. Assassination

of Archduke Franz Ferdinand was not the cause of WWI it was just *casus belli* that brought the inevitable confrontation between two major power blocks faster than expected.

The effects of the pandemic were similar in fashion. Even prior to the pandemic many challenges to the U.S. led order happened – Russian intervention in Georgia, BRICS, annexation of Crimea, Russian involvement in Syria, and the Belt and Road Initiative. While they were far from being a direct challenge to the existing order, they were glimpses of evidence pointing not only to the discontent by some states but also their willingness to act. On a more important note, Chinese economic and military rise over the past decade or so made the process of geopolitical transition bound to happen. When almost all ties to the outside world were severed due to the pandemic, hegemonic presence of the U.S. somewhat faded away. This allowed for action of not only other major powers but lesser states as well to act in a manner they otherwise probably would not. Having that in mind, events took the life of their own which in turn expedited the coming of the period of geopolitical transition. As we see today, “chaos” is the new normality in international affairs, with patterns of state behavior signaling that the structural constraints are lessening their grip on them.

The Notion of Geopolitical Transition

Theoretically speaking, neither Cohen nor Agnew and Corbridge see geopolitical systems as being a static category. International practices and interactions as well as representations and perceptions of geopolitical system are in a constant flux. Of course, they are relatively stable in the sense that we can talk about, let’s say, the Cold War system. But this does not mean that the Cold War geopolitical system was the same in the early 1950s as during the 1980s. From Korea to Vietnam and later on Afghanistan and the Middle East, there were changes in the characteristics of the structure of the world geopolitical system. Likewise, by the final stage of the Cold War, China became the leader of a completely separate geostrategic realm, which was not the case in its early stages. On the other hand, though, throughout the Cold War the same geopolitical discourse existed. But after 1990 things dramatically changed. With the sudden collapse of the U.S.S.R., Eurasian Continental realm lost its momentum, the Balkans “shattered”, Middle East enjoyed a brief moment of tranquility, and Eastern Europe became a temporary gateway region. Simply put, the geopolitical system quickly restructured itself. Similarly, ideological foundation of the predominant discourse went through an overhaul of its own being that the ideological geopolitical discourse gave way to a kind of a liberal-democratic one. But, in all honesty, there hasn’t been an attempt to map the predominant global geopolitical discourse of the post-Cold War system, at least to our knowledge.

Agnew and Corbridge hint that it might be a return to something like the civilizational discourse of the 19th century (apropos Huntington's *Clash of Civilization thesis*) thought they are not definitive on that point.

But this geopolitical system shift was not immediate, in the sense that one replaced the other in the matter of days or weeks following the end of the Cold War. From the fall of the Berlin Wall to the dissolution of the U.S.S.R. couple of year had passed in which there was great uncertainty regarding what's to come. Of course, there had been an understanding that the U.S. would probably be unmatched superpower, but their relations with the Russia that emerged as well as impact on the rest of the world were uncertain. That short period of time represents geopolitical transition. To put it simply, the concept of geopolitical transition relates to the relatively short but rapid period of change in way the world geopolitical system is structured as well as perceived (Taylor, 1990). More often than not, geopolitical transition is the result of a major war, something that Allison calls Thucydides Trap (Allison, 2017). This is obvious because the outcome of major wars virtually always leads to changes in relative power of states, namely those at the top of the "food chain". This produces shocks throughout the system in several different ways. Firstly, characteristics of certain regions change because there is no longer a competitive great power to lead to shatterbelts, or even regional powers for compression zone to emerge. Secondly, regions themselves might be restructured to include states that were previously in other regions or realms. Thirdly, old geostrategic realms might disappear while new ones might emerge. Finally, the discursive basis of the geopolitical system becomes redundant as there is no longer "the other".

While this is also true for the dynamism throughout the "lifespan" of a certain geopolitical system, the main difference is that this happens rapidly – in the span of couple of years, as well as more fundamentally. Having that in mind, it is evident that the concept of geopolitical transition is closely related to the idea of power transition (see: Organski and Kugler, 1980). As in the case of power transition theory, geopolitical transition relates to the change within the structure of the world system as one, or more powers start to decline relative to its/their challengers. But the major point of differentiation is that geopolitical transition is more encompassing. While power transition is necessary for geopolitical transition to unfold, power transition does not necessarily have to lead to a major restructuring of the world geopolitical system both in the sense of structure and discourse. Power transition that happened following WWI, when the U.S. surpassed Great Britain didn't lead to neither a major war nor geopolitical system shifts – thought this is because the U.S. did not want such a role.

When geopolitical transition unfolds structural effects on states become less strong as during periods of relative stability. This is because it becomes debatable whether international structure fully "exists" at that point. Therefore, during periods of

geopolitical transition states are less constrained by the structure. They can reevaluate their position as well as their approach to national security. As Johnston rightfully notices “major geopolitical transitions provide opportunities for political elites in a large number of states to evaluate their country’s international relationships and foreign and defense policies” (Johnston, 1997, p. 63). This reevaluation can lead to states pursuing alternate policies and strategies in order to profit from the permissiveness of the environment in the wake of structural shifts. It is at this point that grand strategic change can, and often does occur.

“The Long 2020”

What we are witnessing since the COVID-19 pandemic started, is that many states are doing precisely that – reevaluating their relationships and foreign and defense policies. Even more so, since 2020, states are even more ready to solve their long-term issues with other states by utilizing force to do so. The nature of the Liberal order was that interstate war was ostracized as a tool of statecraft. While the bipolar world of the Cold War mitigated the institutional and societal grip on legitimate interstate war, the Unipolar Moment broke such practice. In fact, the U.S. were the sole state that had the power to wage war on others – but even then, only with a (relatively) broad international support (see Finnemore, 2003). The reason for this was that world orders tend to lead to a more restrictive strategic environment for states. Once the grip of a world order loosens, the strategic environment becomes more permissive.

The COVID-19 pandemic was the turning point because the internal focus of states on preserving human security of its populus prevented them from major foreign policy action. Well, this is only partially true because each state was willing to focus on foreign policy questions that were of major importance to them. Most states did rely on public diplomacy and foreign aid, but what we are talking about here are the more traditional state behavior in geopolitical studies. This is important for two reasons. Firstly, even during the Pandemic states not only had foreign policy interests, but also acted upon them. Secondly, outside questions of major importance they did not have the resources or the focus to tackle less important questions. The practical implication of this was that the U.S. were unable to manage the world order as they did in the past, which allowed for a more permissive environment.

However, it is important to highlight that the Pandemic was not the cause for the outbreak of the geopolitical transition. Even prior to its beginning there were signs that the world is starting to “shatter” (Kopanja and Stekić, 2020). Relative power between the U.S. and other states was rapidly diminishing and actors both within the U.S. lead Maritime Realm and the Eurasian and East Asian Realms were

beginning to act contrary to U.S. interest. Early turmoil in Ukraine and the start of the Belt and Road Initiative were just the first signs of that. To put it simply, even before the Pandemic hit, there were signs that U.S. unipolarity was no longer unambiguous (see Wohlforth, 1999). While still not a multipolar world, other states in the world system started to perceive the U.S. as no longer the unanimous superpower as it once was. Therefore, the process of geopolitical transition was beginning to show itself even before the COVID-19 Pandemic started. It was nothing more than a catalyst that sped up the process which might have happened not in 2020, but half a decade or so later.

The reason we state that the world order is currently in flux – that is, that we are living in a period of geopolitical transition – is because of the vast increase in conflicts that have happened since 2020. The first major sign was the Armenia-Azerbaijan war over the disputed territory of Nagorno-Karabakh. The dispute between Armenia and Azerbaijan over said territory has been ongoing for more than three decades. The first series of conflicts lasted between 1988 and 1994, with a prolonged period of low-intensity conflict that lasted until 2020. In late September 2020 a 44-day war between the two countries erupted, signifying the first major conflict that excluded the involvement of major powers. Leaving the details of this conflict aside, the 2020 Armenia-Azerbaijan war is significant because it showed that states are once again willing and able to use force to achieve their will – something not seen since at least the end of the Cold War.

Taken on its own, the 2020 Armenia-Azerbaijan war might not have been that relevant had it not been both predated and followed by a series of conflict all around the globe. In the period of 2020-2023 there was much turmoil in many geopolitical regions of the world. In Africa, there were a series of both intrastate conflicts and military coups. Civil wars and conflicts erupted in Ethiopia, Eritrea, Ghana, Somalia, Morocco, Sudan and Nigeria to name a few, with the most important ones being in Ethiopia and Sudan. Likewise, there was a series of coup d'états in Mali, Niger, Guinea, Gabon and Sudan. In Asia, similar events unfolded in Myanmar, between Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan, China and India, as well as Chinese military exercises around Taiwan. However, the two most important events that occurred were the Russo-Ukrainian War and the Israel-Hamas war². When first Russian soldiers entered Ukraine, it came as a sign that the international order has been severely challenged by Russia. Although arguments can be made that Russia has been forced to such action, this does not change the fact that one great power (which is not the U.S.) utilized war as a tool of influencing another state. Simply put,

² Since this paper was presented on the eve of the Hamas attacks on Israel, this case has not been covered in the paper. However, due to the impact it has had this sentence was revised to mention the Israel-Hamas war as well.

an order which was centered around U.S. dominance and to a certain point even governance, has been

Geopolitical theory tells us that when the structure of the world geopolitical system starts to modify, the change is not only rapid but is also violent. For a few years, the world experiences an increase in violent conflicts both between and within states that changes the subsequent political geographical landscape of the world. What we are seeing currently is precisely that – a rapid increase in violent conflicts in the world. Old allegiances are changing, new are forging and *homo homini lupus est* reigns supreme. The COVID-19 pandemic sped up the already unfolding process of world “shattering” by disabling U.S. presence and influence around the world. This created a permissive environment which has led other states to reevaluate their relationships and foreign and defense policies. Such events only further speed up the process of restructuring until, after much blood and destruction, the world system finally restructures itself into a relatively stable new form.

Instead of a conclusion: Great Power Behavior in the “Long 2020”

Assuming that we are living in a period of geopolitical transition, it is therefore undeniable that states will have to change their grand strategies (presuming that all major powers do in fact have them). This begs the question: which states will have to adjust their grand strategy and which will have to overhaul them? We can predict the following – the U.S. will have to completely overhaul their grand strategy, while Russia and China will have to adjust theirs. Everything that the U.S. had done in recent years seems to have had little to no effect on preserving the post-Cold War status quo. They were unable to distribute the burden of security expenses to their NATO allies, prevent projection of Russian power to Ukraine and Syria, block Chinese presence in regions of the world outside their geostrategic realm, as well as maintain their presence in Central Asia. Therefore, an overhaul is needed in order for the U.S. to shape the international order to come towards something reminiscent of the post-Cold War one where their leadership remains, albeit in a less preponderant manner.

On the other hand, Russia and China will have to adjust their grand strategies because, in their current form, do not seem to have a clear picture of the international order that might replace the existing one. Courses of action they had taken in the past decade can be described better in terms of “we don’t want this” than in terms of “we want that”. While knowing what you don’t want is the first step towards determining what it is that you want, you still need to adjust your strategy in order to stop fighting against and work towards building for. On the other hand, they also need not only to envision an order that favors them but also an order which the majority of other states in the international system find

appealing. Without this, they will not be able to legitimize their behavior and will find themselves even more constrained.

As far as lesser (but still powerful) states are concerned we can differentiate them into two groups based on the expectations of changes to their grand strategy. Brazil, India and perhaps even Iran will have to overhaul their grand strategies in the direction of a more active role in shaping the international order. If they let China and Russia to solely shape the international order, they might find themselves in a less favorable situation. This is truer for Brazil and India than Iran, but still we can expect them to overhaul their grand strategies in the coming years. On the other hand, states like Germany, France, the U.K. and Japan will have to adjust their grand strategies in the direction of taking greater and more direct contribution to the U.S. led efforts. So far they have overly relied on the U.S. for their security, therefore relying less on harder forms of power. We can expect that they will follow the U.S.'s approach to the international system in its overhauled form, just as they had for the past three decades, with the adjusted element of taking greater military contribution in these efforts. Finally, Turkey seems to be an exception to the rule. Their grand strategy seems to be reminiscent of something in the lines of a "grand hedge". Since the "no" to the U.S. prior to the invasion of Iraq, they pursued the grand strategy of Strategic depth which focused on its immediate neighborhood (see: Ajzenhamer, 2022). But on a greater level, Turkey seemed to have hedged between the U.S. and NATO on one hand and Russia-China duo on the other hand. The particularity of their position (both in geographic and diplomatic terms) might allow for their grand strategy to continue without overhaul or adjustment.

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